

WETLANDS

Restore4Life

'Wetland' is a broad term to describe an ecosystem on the border of water and land. A few examples include swamps, rivers and saltmarshes

Set 1

Set 2

Set 3

Set 4

BIODIVERSITY

1

1

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In total, about 40% of our planet's species live in wetlands even though these ecosystems only make up around 6% of the land surface.

Wetlands provide breeding grounds, food supply and safety for a lot of species, both marine and terrestrial

Set 1

POLLINATION

2

2

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Wetlands provide habitats and food supplies for pollinators like bees, bumblebees and hoverflies. Our agriculture relies on pollinators to have good harvests

Set 1

WATER SUPPLY

3

3

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Less than 1% of Earth's fresh water is usable and most of that is contained in wetlands, including about a third in rivers and lakes

Set 1

SEDIMENT TRANSPORT

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Rivers and streams supply humans with sand, clay and other sediment to e.g. make building materials like bricks and glass and help protect our coasts by depositing new sediment

Set 1

FLOOD & STORM PROTECTION

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Wetlands like mangrove forests protect the land behind it from the worst damage during storms and floods

Set 1

RECREATION

6

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Rivers, lakes and beaches are often used
to have a good time; in, on or near the
water

Set 1

MEDICAL PURPOSES

7

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Several plants that grow in wetlands like sundew or the white willow are used for medical purposes, both traditionally and in modern medicine

Set 1

CARBON SEQUESTRATION

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The process of storing carbon dioxide long term. It's a critical measure to mitigate climate change. Vegetation uses CO₂ to grow through photosynthesis and in turn store it

HUMAN ACTIVITIES

An aerial photograph of a city, likely Hong Kong, featuring a wide river with several bridges. A prominent bridge with a large red arch spans the river. The city skyline is visible in the background, with numerous high-rise buildings and mountains in the distance. The sky is hazy, suggesting a misty or overcast day.

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The main threat where
the problems start

Set 2

INDUSTRIALISATION

A wide-angle photograph of an industrial facility, likely a refinery or chemical plant, situated along a body of water. On the left, a modern cable-stayed bridge with a prominent blue pylon spans across the water. The industrial complex in the background features various structures, including tall distillation columns, storage tanks, and a large white dome. A tall, white smokestack with two red horizontal bands stands prominently on the right side. Thick plumes of white smoke or steam rise from the facility against a cloudy, overcast sky. The water in the foreground is dark and reflects the industrial scene.

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To build the factories and manufacturing plants, huge areas of forests and wetlands have to make way for the buildings and the infrastructure leading to them

Set 2

OVERFISHING

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Due to very efficient fishing techniques, inadequate monitoring of vessels, apathy and ignorance, the fish populations in wetlands have declined considerably

Set 2

DEGRADATION

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A process where land becomes less productive and healthy. If too much degradation takes place, the wetland ecosystems cannot recover on a short-term basis

An aerial photograph of a terraced rice field, showing rows of vibrant green rice plants growing in a series of stepped, curved terraces that follow the contours of a hillside. The water in the terraces reflects the sky, creating a shimmering effect. The overall scene is a lush, green landscape.

AGRICULTURE

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Rice paddies and palm oil plantations
need a lot of water, which is often
extracted from wetlands

Set 2

OVERUSE OF RESOURCES

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Human beings take too much resources from wetlands; so much that the ecosystems cannot regenerate fast enough to keep up with demand

Set 2

STRUCTURES OBSTRUCTING WATER

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Structures like dams change the flow regime (pattern of the changes a river has annually) and transport of sediment, disrupting a river both up- and downstream

CLIMATE CHANGE

16

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Climate change puts pressure on wetlands due to the global rise in temperature. The intensity and frequency of precipitation can change as well as the amount of evaporation

Set 2

POLLUTION

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Pollution from plastic, PFAS and other toxins seep into the entire ecosystem, including game, vegetation and...

US

FLOODING

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If wetlands are completely removed or degrading, the protective properties vanish with them, making the area behind them prone to flooding

HABITAT LOSS

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Disappearing wetlands mean that there is less room for species to live, some of which are crucial to good harvests or maintaining the balance of the ecosystem

INVASIVE SPECIES

A photograph showing a dense, lush green aquatic plant, likely a water hyacinth, covering a body of water. The leaves are rounded and vibrant green. In the center of the frame, a single, small, light purple flower is in bloom, standing out against the sea of green. The water is dark and reflects the surrounding foliage.

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Species not native to an area or species introduced by humans can cause damage to their new environment by e.g. not having any predators

CONSERVATION

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Conservation is the protection and preservation of something, in this case wetland ecosystems. By assigning a wetland area as protected and monitoring it, people and companies can receive a fine if they e.g. illegally dump waste water in that area

POLICIES

A close-up photograph of a person in a dark suit and white shirt writing on a document with a silver pen. The person's left hand, wearing a black watch and a gold ring, rests on a blue folder. A silver and black fountain pen lies on the wooden desk in the foreground. A laptop is partially visible on the right. A semi-transparent dark grey banner at the top contains the word 'POLICIES' in white. A yellow cross-shaped graphic with the number '22' is overlaid on the bottom left of the document.

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By implementing policies, these can act
as guidelines to aid governmental
decisions

RESTORATION

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By restoring wetlands to their former glory, humans can once again profit from the many benefits that wetlands provide

EDUCATION

A photograph of a classroom. In the foreground, several students are seated at wooden desks, viewed from behind. They are looking towards the front of the room. A teacher, wearing a red and blue plaid shirt, stands at the front near a whiteboard. The classroom has green walls and various educational posters.

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Public awareness and knowledge are important tools to ensure that wetlands and their protection stay in the spotlight. Special days like World Wetland Day also help keeping them relevant

WETLANDS FRESK

Guidelines

Facilitator Guide

The Wetlands Fresk is a collaborative, interactive workshop designed to help participants explore how human activities impact wetland ecosystems (including tidal flats, salt marshes, lagoons, etc.), the consequences of those impacts, and the potential solutions.

Participants work together to build a “map” of cause–effect relationships using a set of cards, and then move toward reflection and action. The aim is not to lecture, but to enable collective intelligence and shared understanding.

Materials and Setup

One complete card set for each group (e.g., 24 cards divided into four thematic sets: Ecosystem Services, Human Activities/ Pressures, Consequences/ Impacts, Solutions/Actions).

Tape or sticky-tack to fix cards in place.

Blank large-format paper or roll, markers/felt pens, arrows or string (to show links), sticky notes for annotations.

A large flat surface (table or wall) for each group to arrange cards.

→ IF DESIRED

Printed workshop worksheet for participants (with space for notes).

→ OPTIONAL

Camera or smartphone to photograph final card-maps.

Room setup

Arrange tables so each group of 4–8 participants has room to move cards and view each other's work. Ensure facilitator(s) can circulate easily. Provide sufficient time and space for the creative/reflective part.

Roles

Facilitator

Guides the process, asks questions, ensures participants stay on track and engage.

Does not dominate or present content.

Co-facilitator

OPTIONAL

Helps monitor each group, supports quieter participants, takes photos or notes.

Participants

Active group members. They read the cards, discuss placements, draw links, reflect, and propose actions.

Phase	Duration	Activity	Facilitator key actions
Introduction	5–10 min	Welcome, explain purpose, present the card set and process.	Set the tone: collaborative, open, non-judgmental. Outline timing and roles.
Phase 1 Discover	~15 min	Participants individually pick cards, read out, discuss what each card means.	Encourage each person to speak; note initial reactions.
Phase 2 Connect the Dots	~25–30 min	Starting with Ecosystem Services, then Pressures, Impacts, and finally Solutions, groups arrange the cards to show cause → effect → response. They draw arrows or strings between the cards to illustrate links.	Circulate among groups, ask probing questions: “Why did you connect these two cards?”, “What leads to this impact?”, “Which pressure affects that service?”
Phase 3 Reflection	~20 min	Each group presents their card-map. Then whole-group discussion: Which connections surprised you? Which impact seems most urgent? Where is the hope?	Facilitate discussion: capture key insights, highlight themes such as hydrology, sediment transport, vegetation development, policy/management measures.
Phase 4 Action Planning	~15–20 min	Groups decide about 2–3 priority actions they can work on to reduce Pressures or Impacts, drafting mini-action plans (what, who, when).	Guide groups to make realistic commitments; ask “What will you do next week/month?”
Closing	~5–10 min	Conclude session: summarise main take-aways, capture photos of card-maps, invite reflections, provide next steps resources.	Thank participants; emphasise how understanding leads to action in their context.

Facilitator Tips

Stay neutral

Your role is facilitative, not didactic.

→ Avoid giving long lectures.

Gentle correction

If a card link seems mis-placed, ask *“Could there be another way to view this?”* rather than immediately re-placing it.

→ Keep in mind there is no perfect or correct way.

Manage time

Gently prompt groups when time is passing

→ Leave sufficient time for the action-planning and reflection.

Mind emotional responses

Some impacts may evoke concern, frustration.

→ Acknowledge emotions and help channel them toward constructive action.

Encourage participation

Ensure everyone speaks

→ invite quieter participants.

Link to context

As you guide, draw attention to the relevance for the participants' region so that the exercise feels connected to their work.

Visual facilitation: Encourage drawing arrows, colour-coding, annotations
→ this helps comprehension and retention.

Follow-up: After the session, send participants a photo of their map, a summary of actions discussed, and any relevant resources you consider.

Understanding the Cards

Each card in the set represents a key concept or element of the wetland system, a human pressure, an ecological consequence, or a solution/intervention.

Ecosystem Services cards

describe what wetlands do (e.g., sediment trapping, biodiversity habitat, flood attenuation, carbon sequestration).

Consequences/Impacts cards

show the ecological, hydrological or socioecological outcomes of the pressures (e.g., loss of habitat, reduced accretion, increased erosion, biodiversity decline).

Human Activities/Pressures cards

Describe anthropogenic actions or disturbances (e.g., dike construction, dredging, land reclamation, pollution, invasive species).

Solutions/Actions cards

represent management, policy or restoration actions (e.g., re-establish tidal connectivity, remove topsoil, monitor vegetation via drones, citizen science programmes).

Participants build links between these layers: pressures affect services, lead to consequences, and require actions.

Workshop Objective & Outcomes

At the end of the workshop, participants should be able to:

Recognise the main services of wetlands and why they matter.
.....

Understand key human pressures on wetland systems and the cascade of impacts that result.
.....

Visualise how different pressures are connected and might amplify or compound each other.

Identify concrete actions that can address specific pressures or impacts, and plan next steps.
.....

Leave with increased motivation and a clearer idea of what they (or their organisation/community) can do.

Pre-session Checklist

Ensure card sets are printed/ready and sorted into thematic sets.

Bring or prepare highlighters, markers, sticky notes, arrow-strings.

Ensure space is arranged for groups and material distribution.

Prepare a camera or phone for photos of final maps.

Prepare a timer or visible clock.

Prepare your follow-up email: include photo, key resources, commitment summary.

